

APH (0.44 ± 0.14 mm) and more slender hull type (L/Wp ; 2.38 ± 0.21) than the first group.

Group 3: possesses mainly allele 3 belonging to the indica type mentioned earlier.

Pgd1 is located on chromosome 11 along with *la*, *v4*, and *Adh1* (Ishikawa et al 1991). Several key resistance genes have already been located on this chromosomal area (Goto 1970), which seemed to be a specific region for upland characters. Landmarks on chromosome 11 were used to obtain restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) markers for constructing a detailed map around *Pgd1*. Sensho and Taichung 65 (Acc. 504) were used to ensure polymorphic regions on chromosome 11. Eleven probes and seven restriction enzymes were used; four of these probes showed polymorphism with some enzymes. Among the probes, *adh1*, G181, and G189 showed allelic band

trends specific to the upland group. The trend of RFLP patterns, however, was less specific than that of *Pgd*. These RFLP markers and *Pgd* are used to arrange several agronomic and stress resistance traits on the chromosome.

Recent plant breeding programs have failed to introduce upland-specific resistance genes into lowland modern varieties. This implies the presence of linkage blocks for useful stress resistance traits of upland cultivars, and also of existing undesirable agronomic traits in lowland varieties. Confirming the chromosomal region where upland-specific markers are located would increase understanding of the origin of Japanese upland rices. Also, detecting RFLP between upland and lowland cultivars will help rice breeders to introduce only useful genetic resources from upland rice into modern varieties.

Cited references

- Glaszmann JC. 1987. Isozyme and classification of Asian rice varieties. *Theor. Appl. Genet.* 74:21-30.
- Goto I. 1970. Genetic studies on the resistance of rice plant to the blast fungus. I. Inheritance of resistance in crosses Sensho x H79 and Imochi-Shiraru X H79. *Ann. Phytopathol. Soc. Jpn.* 36:304-312.
- Ishikawa R, Maeda K, Harada T, Niizeki M, Saito K. 1991. Classification of Japanese rice varieties into Indica and Japonica types by using isozyme genotypes. *Jpn. J. Breed.* 41:605-622.
- Ishikawa R, Morishima H, Kinoshita T, Harada T, Niizeki M, Saito K. 1991. Linkage analysis of nine isozyme genes on the conventional linkage map in rice. *Jpn. J. Breed.* 41:265-272.
- Sano R, Morishima H. 1992. Indica-Japonica differentiation of rice cultivars viewed from the variations in key characters and isozymes, with special reference to landraces from the Himalayan hilly areas. *Theor. Appl. Genet.* 84:266-274. ■

Evolutionary variations in the Gramineae: rearrangements of DNA fragments transferred from chloroplast genomes to mitochondrial genomes

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The transfer of DNA fragments from chloroplast to mitochondrial genomes is considered a general phenomenon in higher plants (Stem and Lonsdale 1982, Stern and Palmer 1984). For rice, Nakazono and Hirai (1993) have determined the entire set of transferred chloroplast sequences present in the mitochondrial genome. Total length of the transferred chloroplast sequences, whose lengths range from 32 bp to 6.8 kb, accounted for about 6% of the rice mitochondrial genome. Two of the 16 identified ct-derived fragments in rice mitochondrial genome, one comprising

rps 19 - trnH - rp12 - rp123 and the other comprising ψ rp123-rbcL-atpB-atpE-trnM-trnV, were found to be separated in the chloroplast genome but were joined in the mitochondrial genome, which might be the cause for homologous recombination between rp123 and rp123. Maize mitochondrial genome also contains these gene clusters (Lonsdale et al 1983).

Watanabe et al (1994) compared this region, which is homologous to chloroplast rps 19 in the mitochondrial genomes, among five gramineous plants (rice, maize, sorghum, Italian rye grass, and wheat) by Southern blot hybridization, polymerase chain reaction (PCR), and DNA sequencing techniques. In all the mitochondrial DNAs from the five gramineous plants — except for that from wheat — the ct-derived fragments of chloroplast DNA were found to be maintained and the same junctions of mitochondrion-specific and chloroplast-like sequences were found at one terminus (rps 19 side). Subsequent analysis revealed that the fragments had been variously rearranged among species with respect to the other terminus. For this region, however, rice rp123 includes a 135-bp deletion in both chloroplast and mitochondrial genomes. In contrast, neither gene in maize has such a deletion. This

suggests that this region must have been transferred separately in rice and maize after their divergence from one another, with subsequent homologous recombination between rp123 and Ψ rp123 in the mitochondrial genomes of rice and maize occurring independently (Fig. 1). These findings indicate that the transfer of the chloroplast sequence occurred in the distant past during the evolution of gramineous plants.

Maintenance of a common junction on one side (the rps19 side), despite the extensive rearrangements of mitochondrial genome, points to the possibility that these sequences might function in the mitochondria. For the result of reverse transcriptase(RT)-PCR and Northern blot hybridization in this study, the chloroplast-derived *trnH* gene was expressed in rice mitochondria (Fig. 2). Comparisons of such ct-derived fragments among or within species may provide some interesting information about the evolution of mitochondrial genomes.

Cited references

- Stem DB, Lonsdale DM. 1992. Mitochondrial and chloroplast genomes of maize have a 12-kilobase DNA sequence in common. *Nature* 299:698-702.

1. Schematic representation of possible transfer and homologous recombination of ct-derived DNA fragments. Event I (transfer of DNA fragment from chloroplast to mitochondrial genome) occurred before the divergence of rice and maize. Events II (secondary DNA transfer from chloroplast to mitochondrial genome) and III (homologous recombination) occurred after the divergence of rice and maize.

Stern DB, Palmer JD. 1984. Extensive and widespread homologies between mitochondrial DNA and chloroplast DNA in plants. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 81:1946-1950.

Nakazono M, Hirai A. 1993. Identification of the entire set of transferred chloroplast DNA sequences in the mitochondrial genome on rice. *Mol. Gen. Genet.* 236:341-346.

Watanabe N, Nakazono M, Kanno A, Tsutsumi N, Hirai A. 1994. Evolutionary variations in DNA sequences transferred from chloroplast genomes to mitochondrial genomes in the Gramineae. *Curr. Genet.* 26:512-518.

Lonsdale DM, Hodge TP, Howe CJ, Stern DB. 1983. Maize mitochondrial of DNA contains a sequence homologous to the ribulose-1, 5-bisphosphate carboxylase large subunit gene of chloroplast DNA. *Cell* 34:1007-1014. ■

2. Gene expression of the ct-derived DNA fragment in mitochondrial genome. (a) Positions of primers for PCR experiment are indicated by P1 and P2. (b) RT-PCR experiment. Total RNA was prepared from rice green leaves and cDNA were synthesized (or not synthesized) with reverse transcriptase (RT+/RT-) using P2 primer. M = molecular weight marker of Φ X174 DNA digested with *Hae* III. (c) Northern hybridization was carried out using nonradioactively labeled probes, indicated under each Northern hybridization pattern. Oligo-trnfM and B9 KpnI 1.8 kb are specific probes for mitochondrial and chloroplast tRNA, respectively. Lane 1 = rice mtRNA; lane 2 = total RNA extracted from green leaves; lane 3 = total RNA extracted from etiolated leaves.